

INTEGER CIRCULANT DETERMINANTS OF ORDER 15

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Abstract

We consider the values taken by $n \times n$ circulant determinants with integer entries when n is the product of two distinct odd primes p, q . These correspond to the integer group determinants for \mathbb{Z}_{pq} , the cyclic group of order pq . We show that p^2 and q^2 are not determinants (more generally we show that the classic necessary divisibility conditions are never sufficient when n contains at least two distinct odd primes). We obtain a complete description of the integer group determinants for \mathbb{Z}_{15} (the smallest unresolved group) and partial results for general $n = 3p$.

1. Introduction

We recall that a *circulant determinant* is one where successive rows arise by a cyclic shift of the previous row one step to the right

$$D(a_0, \dots, a_{n-1}) := \det \begin{pmatrix} a_0 & a_1 & \dots & a_{n-1} \\ a_{n-1} & a_0 & \dots & a_{n-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

At the 1977 meeting of the American Mathematical Society in Hayward, California, Olga Taussky-Todd asked which integers can be obtained as an integral $n \times n$ circulant determinant:

$$S_n := \{D(a_0, \dots, a_{n-1}) : (a_0, \dots, a_{n-1}) \in \mathbb{Z}^n\}.$$

For a finite group G , and $|G|$ variables a_g , $g \in G$, the group determinant is defined to be the polynomial obtained by taking the determinant of the matrix whose ij th entry is $a_{g_i g_j^{-1}}$. One can similarly ask what integer values the group determinants

take when the variables a_g are all integral. The group determinant polynomial determines the group [8], but it remains open whether the integer values determine the group. Determining S_n is plainly the same as determining the integer group determinants in the special case of the cyclic group

$$\mathbb{Z}_n = \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\} \text{ mod } n.$$

In [20] a complete description of the integer group determinants was obtained for all groups with $|G| \leq 14$. Partial results have been obtained for other families of finite groups, [2, 3, 6, 7, 16, 21, 22]. Here we consider the smallest unresolved group \mathbb{Z}_{15} , the 15×15 integer circulant determinants S_{15} . As observed by Newman [17] (or using characters to factor the group determinant, see for example [4]), we can write

$$D(a_0, \dots, a_{n-1}) = M_n(a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_{n-1}x^{n-1})$$

where for a polynomial $F(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ we define

$$M_n(F) := \prod_{j=1}^n F(\omega_n^j), \quad \omega_n := e^{2\pi i/n}. \tag{1}$$

It will often be convenient to break this down as a product of integer norms

$$M_n(F) := \prod_{d|n} N_d(F), \quad N_d(F) := \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ \gcd(j,d)=1}}^d F(\omega_d^j), \tag{2}$$

by dividing the n th roots of unity into the various primitive d th roots of unity. We can think of $M_n(F)$ as the resultant of F with $x^n - 1$ and the $N_d(F)$ the resultants with its irreducible factors, the d th cyclotomic polynomials:

$$\Phi_n(x) := \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ \gcd(j,n)=1}}^n (x - \omega_n^j), \quad x^n - 1 = \prod_{d|n} \Phi_d(x).$$

Note, we can recover a circulant determinant from a polynomial of degree n or more by reducing mod $(x^n - 1)$. See [9, 10, 15] for a discussion of $\frac{1}{n} \log |M_n(F)|$ as a \mathbb{Z}_n group generalization of the classical logarithmic Mahler Measure, or [5] for an alternative approach. In [19] the smallest non-trivial value, the counterpart of the classical Lehmer Problem [13], was obtained for all cyclic groups of order less than 892, 371, 480.

Trivially S_n is closed under multiplication (from Equation (2) or by multiplying elements $\sum_{g \in G} a_g g$ in the group ring). Other elementary properties were obtained in Newman [17] and Lacquer [12]. For example,

$$\{m \in \mathbb{Z} : \gcd(m, n) = 1\} \cup n^2\mathbb{Z} \subset S_n; \tag{3}$$

to be explicit, $M_n(-x) = -1$ and if $\gcd(m, n) = 1$

$$M_n \left(\prod_{p^\alpha \parallel m} \Phi_p(x)^\alpha \right) = |m|, \quad M_n \left(1 - x + k \left(\frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1} \right) \right) = kn^2.$$

We shall frequently use that the absolute value of the resultant of two cyclotomic polynomials $\Phi_k(x)$ and $\Phi_s(x)$, $k > s$, is $p^{\phi(s)}$ if $k = sp^\alpha$ and one otherwise (see for example [1, 14]). Newman and Laquer also obtained the divisibility restrictions

$$t \in S_n, \quad p \mid t, \quad p^\alpha \parallel n \Rightarrow p^{\alpha+1} \mid t. \tag{4}$$

For odd primes p this led them to a precise description of S_p and S_{2p} ,

$$S_p = \{p^a m \ : \ \gcd(m, p) = 1, \ a = 0 \text{ or } a \geq 2\}$$

and

$$S_{2p} = \{2^a p^b m \ : \ \gcd(m, 2p) = 1, \ a = 0 \text{ or } a \geq 2, \ b = 0 \text{ or } b \geq 2\},$$

with Property (4) being an if and only if condition. While Property (4) is always sharp, in the sense that

$$p^\alpha \parallel n \Rightarrow p^{\alpha+j} \parallel M_n(x - 1 + p^j) \text{ for all } j \geq 1,$$

we will not in general obtain all multiples of $p^{\alpha+1}$. For example, Newman [18] showed that $p^{\alpha+1} \notin S_{p^\alpha}$ for any $\alpha \geq 2$ when $p \geq 5$. Here we show a similar negative result for the prime powers in S_n when n contains more than one odd prime.

Theorem 1. *Suppose that n is divisible by two distinct odd primes p and q with $p^\alpha \parallel n$. Then $p^{\alpha+1}$ is not in S_n .*

We concentrate on the case $n = pq$ where p and q are distinct odd primes. From Property (4) the only determinants, in addition to the Inclusion (3), must be of the form $p^2 m$, $q \nmid m$ and $q^2 m$, $p \nmid m$. But from Theorem 1 not all integers of this form will be determinants, for example, p^2 and q^2 are not themselves determinants. In all cases of $n = 3p$ (and a couple of cases of $n = 5p$ that we tested computationally) we do though obtain all such multiples of p^3 and q^3 .

Theorem 2. *Let p and q be distinct odd primes. For the cases $pq = 3p, 35,$ or 55 , we have*

$$\{p^3 m \ : \ \gcd(m, q) = 1\} \cup \{q^3 m \ : \ \gcd(m, p) = 1\} \subset S_{pq}. \tag{5}$$

This follows immediately from the lemmas in Section 3 below.

Question 1. Does Inclusion (5) in fact hold for all distinct odd primes p and q ?

Determining precisely which multiples 3^2m and p^2m , $\gcd(m, 3p) = 1$, are determinants for $n = 3p$ would seem to be a much harder problem. Our goal here is only to make this explicit for $n = 15$. It helps here that we have uniqueness of factorization in all the underlying cyclotomic extensions $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_n]$, $n = 3, 5$ and 15 (see for example Washington [24, Theorem 11.1]). It will require us to divide the primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$ into two classes according to their representation as a 15-norm; we shall see that every $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$ can be written in the form

$$p = N_{15}((x^5 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x)B(x) + (x - 1)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)g(x))$$

for some $g(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, $0 \leq j < 15$, and either $B(x) = 1$ (we shall call these primes *good*) or $B(x) = (x - 1)$ (we shall call these primes *bad*).

Theorem 3. *The determinants in S_{15} take the form $15^2\mathbb{Z}$ or m or $3^t m, 5^t m$ with $t \geq 3$, or $3^2 k, 5^2 k$ with*

(i) $k = mp, p \equiv 7, 11$ or $13 \pmod{15}$, or a “good” $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$, or

(ii) $k = mp^2, p \equiv 4 \pmod{15}$, or

(iii) $k = mp^4, p \equiv 2$ or $8 \pmod{15}$,

where m can be any integer coprime to 15 and p denotes a prime.

The downside is that it is not immediately obvious which primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$ are good. For example, the *good* $p \leq 5000$, for which we can obtain $3^2 p$ and $5^2 p$, are

31, 151, 181, 421, 601, 661, 691, 751, 811, 1051, 1171, 1231, 1291, 1321, 1531, 1621, 1741, 1831, 1861, 2221, 2281, 2371, 2521, 2551, 2971, 3061, 3181, 3271, 3301, 3361, 3391, 3511, 3691, 4051, 4111, 4201, 4231, 4561, 4621, 4831, 4951,

and the *bad* primes

61, 211, 241, 271, 331, 541, 571, 631, 991, 1021, 1201, 1381, 1471, 1801, 1951, 2011, 2131, 2161, 2251, 2311, 2341, 2671, 2791, 2851, 3001, 3121, 3331, 3541, 3571, 3631, 3931, 4021, 4261, 4441, 4591, 4651, 4801, 4861.

The complexity that we encountered for $n = 3p$ for $p = 5$ did not make us want to attempt this for larger p , although $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{3p}]$ does have uniqueness of factorization for $p = 7$ or 11 .

2. Proof of Theorem 1

Lemma 1. *If $u(x)$ is in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ and $u(\omega_n)$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_n]$, then $u(\omega_n^{-1}) = \varepsilon \omega_n^J u(\omega_n)$ for some integer $J \geq 0$ and $\varepsilon = \pm 1$. If $n = p^\alpha$ is an odd prime power, then $\varepsilon = +1$.*

Proof. Since $u(\omega_n)$ is a unit we know that $\alpha = u(\omega_n^{-1})/u(\omega_n)$ is an algebraic integer with $|\alpha| = 1$. The same is true for all its conjugates and hence α , by Kronecker's Theorem [11], must be a root of unity in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_n]$. So $\alpha = \pm\omega_n^J$ for some integer $J \geq 0$.

If $n = p^\alpha$ is an odd prime power, then $u(\omega_n)^n, u(\omega_n^{-1})^n \equiv u(1) \pmod{p}$, and we can rule out $\varepsilon = -1$, since then $0 = u(\omega_n^{-1})^n + u(\omega_n)^n \equiv 2u(\omega_n)^n \pmod{p}$ but, being a unit, $|u(\omega_n)|_p = 1$ for the extension of the p -adic absolute value to $\mathbb{Q}(\omega_n)$. \square

For odd n one could use this to deduce that the units in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_n]$ take the form $\pm\omega_n^k$ or $\pm\omega_n^k(1 - \omega_n)$ times a real unit $P(\omega_n + \omega_n^{-1})$, with only the first form needed if n is a prime power; see more generally Washington [24, Corollary 4.13].

Proof of Theorem 1. Since for $\gcd(s, t) = 1$ and F in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ we have

$$M_{st}(F) = M_s(G), \quad G(x) = \prod_{j=1}^t F(x\omega_t^j) \in \mathbb{Z}[x],$$

we can assume that $n = p^\alpha q^\ell$. Suppose that $F(x)$ is a polynomial in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ of degree d with $M_n(F) = p^{\alpha+1}$.

Since for $\gcd(r, p) = 1$ we have $N_{rp^j}(F) \equiv N_r(F)^{\phi(p^j)} \pmod{p}$, we readily see that $M_{p^\alpha q^\ell}(F) = p^{\alpha+1}$ can only happen when $N_{p^j q^\beta}(F) = p$ for some $0 \leq \beta \leq \ell$ and all $0 \leq j \leq \alpha$, with $N_{p^j q^\beta}(F) = 1$ if $s \neq \beta$. We split into two cases, $\beta = 0$ and $\beta \geq 1$. Notice that the second can only happen when $p = N_{q^\beta}(F) \equiv F(1)^{\phi(q^\beta)} \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$.

Case (i): We have $N_{pq}(F) = 1, N_p(F) = p, N_q(F) = 1$.

If $N_{pq}(F) = 1$, then $F(\omega_{pq})$ is a unit and, by Lemma 1, $\omega_{pq}^d F(\omega_{pq}^{-1}) = \varepsilon \omega_{pq}^J F(\omega_{pq})$ with $\varepsilon = 1$ or -1 and some $J \geq 0$. Hence we have a polynomial expression

$$x^d F(x^{-1}) = \varepsilon x^J F(x) + \Phi_{pq}(x)h(x),$$

for some $h(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

Suppose that $N_p(F) = p^\delta$, then $F(\omega_p) = (1 - \omega_p)^\delta v(\omega_p)$, where $v(\omega_p)$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_p]$ and so $\omega_p^d F(\omega_p^{-1}) = (-1)^\delta (1 - \omega_p)^\delta \omega_p^{J'} v(\omega_p) = (-1)^\delta \omega_p^{J'} F(\omega_p)$.

Observing that $\Phi_{pq}(\omega_p) = q\Phi_q(\omega_p)^{-1}$ we get

$$(-1)^{p\delta} F(\omega_p)^p \equiv \varepsilon^p F(\omega_p)^p \pmod{q}.$$

Since $|F(\omega_p)|_q = 1$ we deduce that $(-1)^\delta = \varepsilon$. Reversing the primes we see that $N_{pq}(F) = 1, N_p(F) = p^\delta, N_q(F) = q^{\delta'}$ forces $(-1)^\delta = (-1)^{\delta'} = \varepsilon$ ruling out $\delta, \delta' = 1, 0$ or $0, 1$.

Case (ii). We have $N_{pq^\beta}(F) = p$ for some $\beta \geq 1$, and $N_p(F) = 1$.

From $N_{pq^\beta}(F) = p$ we can write

$$V := \text{Norm}_{\mathbb{Q}(\omega_{pq^\beta})/\mathbb{Q}(\omega_p)} F(\omega_{pq^\beta}) = \prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_{pq^\beta}^j), \quad \text{Norm}_{\mathbb{Q}(\omega_p)/\mathbb{Q}}(V) = p,$$

where we can take \mathcal{J} to be the $\phi(q^\beta)$ values of $j \pmod{pq^\beta}$ with $j \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, $q \nmid j$. Hence $V = (1 - \omega_p)v(\omega_p)$ where $v(\omega_p)$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_p]$, and by Lemma 1

$$\prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_{pq^\beta}^{-j}) = (1 - \omega_p^{-1})v(\omega_p^{-1}) = -\omega_p^J V$$

for some J , giving us the polynomial relationship

$$x^{pd \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} j} \prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(x^j)^p + \prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} x^{pj d} F(x^{-j})^p = \Phi_{pq^\beta}(x)h(x), \tag{6}$$

for some $h(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$. Now if $N_p(F) = 1$, then $\prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_p^j)$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_p]$ and Lemma 1 gives $\prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_p^{-j}) = \omega_p^{J'} \prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_p^j)$ for some J' . But then from Equation (6)

$$\Phi_{pq^\beta}(x) = \Phi_{q^\beta}(x^p)\Phi_{q^\beta}(x)^{-1} \Rightarrow 2 \prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_p^j)^p \equiv 0 \pmod{q},$$

a contradiction as the unit $\left| \prod_{j \in \mathcal{J}} F(\omega_p^j)^p \right|_q = 1$. □

In the proof of Theorem 1 for $n = pq$ we needed to separately consider the possibility of $N_{pq}(F) = p$ with $N_p(F) = 1$. It seems natural to ask when this can occur.

Question 2. For which $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ is there an F in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ with $N_{pq}(F) = p$?

We only discovered one case of this, namely $N_{21}(x^4 + x - 1) = 7$. Indeed, as shown in Lemma 2 below, any examples must have $q = 3, p \equiv 7 \pmod{12}$ or $q \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, p \equiv 1 \pmod{4q}$.

Checking the first few $p \equiv 7 \pmod{12}$, for $p = 19, 31, 43, 67$ or 79 there is no F in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ with $N_{3p}(F) = p$. For $p = 19$ one can check this directly in Magma, though there is an F in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. For the remaining primes one can check that there is no algebraic integer of norm p in the degree $2(p-1)/6$ subfield $\mathbb{Q}\left(\sqrt{3i \sum_{j=1}^6 \omega_p^{r(p-1)j/6}}\right)$, r a primitive root mod p , though again there are elements of norm p in the field.

Checking the first 100 cases, there are no $N_n(F) = p$ with $n = pq \leq 25, 105$ and $q \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, p \equiv 1 \pmod{4q}$. Of these, 83 could be ruled out just by checking that p was not the norm of an algebraic integer in the quadratic field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{n})$ (note this will not rule out cases such as $p = 4q+1, q = 13, 37, 53, 73, \dots$, where $p^2 - n \cdot 2^2 = p$), the other 17 using Magma and the degree $2k$ field $\mathbb{Q}\left(\left(\sum_{j=1}^{(q-1)/k} \omega_q^{r^{kj}}\right)\sqrt{p}\right)$, where r is a primitive root mod q , with $k = 4$ for $(q, p) = (5, p), p = 181, 761, 1021, 1621, 1741, 2441, 2801, 3581, 3881, 4861, (13, p), p = 53, 1301, 1873, (17, 613), (37, p), p = 149, 593$ and $k = 8$ for $(73, 293)$.

Rachel Newton has pointed out to us that [25] could probably be used to decide when there are solutions to $N_{pq}(F) = p$ with F in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. See also [23].

Lemma 2. *Suppose that p, q are primes with $p \equiv 1 \pmod q$. If $pq \equiv 3 \pmod 4$, or $p, q \equiv 3 \pmod 4$ with $q \geq 7$, then there is no F in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ with $N_{pq}(F) = p$.*

Proof. For $pq \equiv 3 \pmod 4$, set $L = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-pq}) \subset \mathbb{Q}(\omega_{pq})$. If $p = N_{pq}(F)$, then $p = \text{Norm}_{L/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha)$, $\alpha = \text{Norm}_{\mathbb{Q}(\omega_{pq})/L}(F(\omega_{pq}))$. But p is not the norm of an algebraic integer in L , since $x^2 + pqy^2 = 4p$ plainly has no integer solution. For $p, q \equiv 3 \pmod 4$, $p \equiv 1 \pmod q$, we use the degree $(q - 1)$ subfield $L = \mathbb{Q}(2 \cos(2\pi/q)\sqrt{pi})$, and suppose that there is an algebraic integer $\alpha = g(\cos(2\pi/q)) + i\sqrt{p} h(\cos(2\pi/q))$ in L with $p = N_{L/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha)$. Now

$$\begin{aligned} N_{L/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha) &= \prod_{j=1}^{(q-1)/2} \left(g(\cos(2\pi j/q))^2 + p h(\cos(2\pi j/q))^2 \right) \\ &\geq \prod_{j=1}^{(q-1)/2} p h(\cos(2\pi j/q))^2 = N_{L/\mathbb{Q}}\left(2i\sqrt{p} h(\cos(2\pi/q))\right) / 2^{q-1} = m/2^{q-1}, \end{aligned}$$

where m is the norm of an algebraic integer $\alpha - \bar{\alpha}$ and so is in \mathbb{N} . Note $m \neq 0$ since $N_{L/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha) = N_{\mathbb{Q}(\cos(2\pi/q))/\mathbb{Q}}(g(\cos(2\pi/q))^2)$ is a square and so cannot equal p . Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod q$ we know that \mathbb{Q}_p already contains the q th roots of unity. Hence for $v \mid p$ we have $|2i h(\cos(2\pi j/q))|_v = p^k$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $|2i\sqrt{p} h(\cos(2\pi j/q))|_v = p^{-\frac{1}{2}+k} \leq p^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, since $|\alpha - \bar{\alpha}|_v \leq 1$, giving $|m|_v \leq p^{-(q-1)/2}$ and $p^{(q-1)/2} \mid m$. But $p \geq p^{(q-1)/2}/2^{q-1}$ leads to $(p/4)^{(q-3)/2} \leq 4$ and a contradiction for $q \geq 7$. \square

3. Constructing the Multiples of p^3 and 3^3 in S_{3p}

Using the following lemma we can get p^3m , $3 \nmid m$, as a \mathbb{Z}_{3p} determinant.

Lemma 3. *Suppose that $2mp \equiv k \pmod 3$ with $k = 1$ or 2 , then*

$$F(x) = \left(\frac{x^{mp+2k} - 1}{x - 1}\right) - x^{2mp-k} \left(\frac{x^k - 1}{x - 1}\right) (x^{3k} + 1) \quad \text{has} \quad M_{3p}(F) = p^3m.$$

Similarly, we can get any 3^3m , $p \nmid m$, as a \mathbb{Z}_{3p} determinant.

Lemma 4. *If $p \nmid m$, then*

$$F_3(x) = \left(\frac{x^{3p-9} - 1}{x - 1}\right) - x^{3p-6}(1+x^3+x^6) \left(\frac{x^{p-3-3m} - 1}{x - 1}\right) \quad \text{has} \quad M_{3p}(F_3) = 3^4m,$$

multiplying by a power of x to make a polynomial if $3m > p - 3$.

For $\text{gcd}(m, 3p) = 1$ trivially

$$F_4(x) = (1 + x^3 + x^6) \prod_{q^\alpha \parallel m} \Phi_q^\alpha(x) \quad \text{has} \quad M_{3p}(F_4) = 3^3|m|.$$

Proof of Lemma 3. The value at $x = 1$ gives $N_1(F) = (mp + 2k) - 2k = mp$. When x is a primitive cube root of unity we get $F(x) = \left(\frac{x^k - 1}{x - 1}\right) (1 - 2)$ and $N_3(F) = 1$.

When x is a primitive p th root of unity we get

$$F(x) = \left(\frac{x^{2k} - 1}{x - 1}\right) (1 - x^{-k} (x^{2k} - x^k + 1)) = -x^{-k} (x^{2k} - 1) \frac{(x^k - 1)^2}{(x - 1)}$$

and $N_p(F) = p^2$.

When x is a primitive $3p$ th root, we have $x^{2m'p} + x^{m'p} + 1 = 0$ for $3 \nmid m'$, and with $m' = m, 2m$,

$$\begin{aligned} (x - 1)F(x) &= x^{mp+2k} - 1 - x^{2mp+3k} - x^{2mp} + x^{2mp-k} + x^{2mp+2k} \\ &= x^{4mp} - x^{2k} - x^{2mp+3k} + x^{2mp-k} = x^{2k}(x^{2mp-3k} - 1)(x^{2mp+k} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

giving a contribution $N_{3p}(F) = 1$ (since the resultant of Φ_{3p} and Φ_d will be trivial unless d is a prime power multiple of $3p$ or 3 or p). \square

Proof of Lemma 4. Plainly $x = 1$ contributes $N_1(F_3) = (3p - 9) - 3(p - 3 - 3m) = 9m$. For a $3p$ th root of unity $x \neq 1$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} x^9 F_3(x) &= -\frac{1}{x - 1} (x^9 - 1 + x^3(1 + x^3 + x^6)(x^{p-3-3m} - 1)) \\ &= -(1 + x^3 + x^6) \frac{(x^{p-3m} - 1)}{(x - 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

For the primitive cube-roots this gives $-3\Phi_p(x)$ and $N_3(F_3) = 9$. For the primitive p th and $3p$ th roots we get plus or minus a power of x , $\Phi_9(x)$ and $\Phi_d(x)$ with $d > 1$ dividing $|p - 3m|$. None of these cyclotomics having order differing from p or $3p$ by a prime power, so contribute $N_p(F_3) = N_{3p}(F_3) = 1$.

For F_4 , plainly $M_{3p}(1 + x^3 + x^6) = 27$, with the remaining factor contributing the $|m|$ as usual when $\gcd(3p, m) = 1$. \square

For $n = 35$ or 55 we can get p^3 from

$$M_{35}(1 + x^3 + x^5 + x^7 + x^{10}) = M_{55}(1 + x^3 + x^5 + x^7 + x^{10}) = 5^3$$

and

$$M_{35} \left(\left(\frac{x^9 - 1}{x - 1} \right) - x^3(x^2 + 1) \right) = 7^3, \quad M_{55} \left(x^{14} + 1 + x^3 \left(\frac{x^9 - 1}{x - 1} \right) \right) = 11^3.$$

For $\gcd(k, n) = 1$ and $F(1) \neq 0$ we have

$$G(x) = \left(\frac{x^k - 1}{x - 1}\right) F(x) + \lambda \left(\frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1}\right) \Rightarrow M_n(G) = \left(\frac{kF(1) + \lambda n}{F(1)}\right) M_n(F),$$

and, since in the above examples $F(1) = p$, taking $k = mp^t - q$, $\lambda = 1$ gives $M_n(G) = mp^{t+3}$ for any $t \geq 1$ and $q \nmid m$, with the mp^3 following from $k = m$, $\lambda = 0$ or Inclusion (3) and closure under multiplication.

4. Good or Bad 15-norms

We begin by showing that elements in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$ that have 15-norm coprime to 15 can be written in one of two ways.

Lemma 5. *Suppose that ξ is in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$ with $\gcd(N_{15}(\xi), 15) = 1$, then*

$$\xi = u_1F_1(\omega_{15}) = u_2F_2(\omega_{15})$$

where u_1, u_2 are units in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$ and

$$F_1(x) = (x^5 - 1) \pm x^j\Phi_3(x)B(x) + (x - 1)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)g_1(x),$$

$$F_2(x) = (x^3 - 1) \pm x^{j'}\Phi_5(x)B(x) + (x - 1)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)g_2(x),$$

for some $g_1(x), g_2(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, integers $0 \leq j, j' < 15$, and either $B(x) = 1$ or $(x - 1)$.

We shall say that ξ is *good* if $B(x) = 1$ and *bad* if $B(x) = (x - 1)$.

Proof. Suppose that $k = N_{15}(F)$ with $\gcd(k, 15) = 1$. Then from

$$1 = -x\Phi_5(x) + (x^3 + 1)\Phi_3(x)$$

we can write

$$F(x) = \alpha(x)(x^5 - 1) + \beta(x)\Phi_3(x) - F(1)\Phi_5(x)\Phi_{15}(x),$$

with

$$\alpha(x) = \frac{(F(1)\Phi_{15}(x) - xF(x))}{x - 1}, \quad \beta(x) = (x^3 + 1)F(x).$$

Dividing through by $\Phi_3(x)$ and reducing the coefficients of the remainder mod 5

$$\alpha(x) = A(x) + 5t_1(x) + q_1(x)\Phi_3(x), \quad A(x) = Ax + B, \quad A, B \in \{0, \pm 1, \pm 2\}.$$

We can rule out $A = B = 0$ since $5 \nmid k$. For the case A or $B = 0$ or $A = \pm B \neq 0$ we note that

$$2x = (x - 1)^2 - \Phi_3(x) + 5x, \quad (x + 1) = \Phi_3(x) - x^2,$$

and for the nonzero A, B with $A \neq \pm B$ that

$$2x + 1 = \Phi_3(x) - x(x - 1), \quad x + 2 = (2 - x)\Phi_3(x) + x^2(x - 1),$$

$$x - 2 = 2x(x - 1) - 2\Phi_3(x) + 5x, \quad 2x - 1 = (4 - 2x)\Phi_3(x) + 2x^2(x - 1) - 5.$$

Hence we can adjust $q_1(x)$ and $t_1(x)$ to replace $A(x)$ by

$$A(x) = \pm x^j(x - 1)^i, \quad 0 \leq i \leq 3.$$

Here we are only considering $F(x)$ on the 15th roots of unity so we are allowed to replace x^j with $x^{j \bmod 15}$ if j is negative.

Replacing $\beta(x)$ by $(x - 1)\beta_1(x) + \beta(1)\Phi_{15}(x)$ and repeating as necessary we can write

$$\beta(x)\Phi_3(x) = (x - 1)^i\beta_2(x)\Phi_3(x) + s_1(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_{15}(x).$$

Dividing by $\Phi_5(x)$ and reducing mod 3

$$\beta_2(x) = B(x) + 3t_2(x) + q_2(x)\Phi_5(x), \quad B(x) = a_3x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_1x + a_0, \quad a_\ell \in \{0, \pm 1\}.$$

We cannot have all the $a_\ell = 0$ since $3 \nmid k$. Now, we are allowed to adjust by $x^5 - 1$ (by altering $q_2(x)$), so that introducing an appropriate power of x we can think of $B(x)$ as 5 coefficients a_0, \dots, a_4 arranged cyclically, with at most 4 of them ± 1 . If we have 4 of them nonzero, then we will have at least two coefficients the same sign and by subtracting or adding a $\Phi_5(x)$ as the value is 1 or -1 and reducing mod 3 we can reduce to at most 3 nonzero terms. A single term corresponds to $\pm x^j$ and two nonzero terms to $\pm x^j(x \pm 1)$ or $\pm x^j(x^2 \pm 1)$. If we have three terms and all are the same, then adding or subtracting a $\Phi_5(x)$ reduces to two nonzero terms. If all are consecutive in the cycle we get $\pm x^j(x^2 - x + 1)$ or $\pm x^j(1 + x - x^2)$ or $\pm x^j(1 - x - x^2)$. If non-consecutive, then we have two consecutive with one gap either end reducing to $\pm x^j(1 + x - x^3)$, $\pm x^j(1 - x + x^3)$ or $\pm x^j(1 - x - x^3)$, where we can write $1 + x - x^3 = \Phi_5(x) - 3x^3 - x^2(1 - x + x^2)$.

Thus, multiplying through by a power of x , changing the $M_{15}(F)$ by at most a sign, we can assume that

$$F(x) = (x - 1)^i((x^5 - 1) \pm x^j\Phi_3(x)B(x)) + 5t_1(x)(x^5 - 1) + 3t_2(x)\Phi_3(x) + t_3(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x) + t_4(x)\Phi_{15}(x) \quad (7)$$

where $B(x)$ is either a Type 1:

$$1, x + 1, x^2 + 1 \text{ or } 1 - x + x^2, \quad (8)$$

or a Type 2:

$$x - 1, x^2 - 1, 1 + x - x^2, 1 - x - x^2, 1 - x - x^3 \text{ or } 1 - x + x^3. \quad (9)$$

So far we have preserved the values at all the 15th roots of unity; we will need this decomposition in the proof of Theorem 3. For the Lemma we just need to preserve the value at the primitive 15th roots of unity, up to multiplication by a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$. Type 1 will give us the good cases and Type 2 the bad.

For a primitive 15th root of unity x we have

$$(x - 1)^{-1} = (x^2 - 1)(x^4 - 1)(x^7 - 1)(x^8 - 1)(x^{11} - 1)(x^{13} - 1)(x^{14} - 1)$$

and

$$3 = (x^5 - 1)(x^{10} - 1), 5 = (x^3 - 1)(x^6 - 1)(x^9 - 1)(x^{12} - 1),$$

hence we can divide through by $(x - 1)^i$ and up to a unit replace F by

$$F(x) = (x^5 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x)B(x) + g_3(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x).$$

When $B(x) = (x + 1)$ or $(x^2 + 1)$ multiplying through by the other gives $(x^2 + 1)(x + 1) = -x^4 + \Phi_5(x)$, and when $B(x) = 1 - x + x^2$ multiplying by $(x + 1)^2$ gives $(x^3 + 1)(x + 1) = -x^2 + \Phi_5(x)$, reducing the Type 1 to $B(x) = 1$, where since $(1 + x), (1 + x^2)$ are $-x^2$ or $-x \pmod{\Phi_3}$ this just changes $(x^5 - 1)$ by a power of x which can be divided out. Similarly,

$$(1+x-x^2)(1+x^2) = x^2(x^2-1)+\Phi_5(x)-3x^4, (1-x-x^2)(1+x^2) = (x^2-1)-\Phi_5(x)+3,$$

$$(1-x-x^3)(1+x) = (x-1)-\Phi_5(x)+3, (1-x+x^3)(1+x) = x(x-1)+\Phi_5(x)-3x^2,$$

with multiplication by $(x^2 + 1)$ removing the $(x + 1)$, reducing $(x^2 - 1)$ to $(x - 1)$. Hence in Type 2 we can always reduce to $B(x) = (x - 1)$. Thus for x a 15th root of unity we have shown

$$F(x) = u((x^5 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x)B(x) + g_3(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x))$$

with u a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ and $B(x) = 1$, which we will call a good case (from Type 1), or $B(x) = (x - 1)$, which we will call bad (from Type 2). Notice we can always replace $g_3(x)$ by $g_3(x) - g_3(1)\Phi_{15}(x)$ and hence the $g_3(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)$ by $g_4(x)(x - 1)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)$ as stated in the Lemma.

When $B(x) = (x - 1)$ we plainly obtain the second form with $j' = 15 - j$ by dividing by $\pm x^j$. When $B(x) = 1$ we multiply by $x^4(x + 1)$, where for the first term $x^4(x + 1) = -x^6 + x^4\Phi_3(x)$ and for the second

$$x^4(x + 1) = (x + 1)\Phi_{15}(x) - (x - 1)^2(x^4 - \Phi_5(x))(x^2 - \Phi_5(x)),$$

and get

$$-x^6((x^5 - 1) \pm x^j(x^3 - 1)(x - 1)) + (x - 1)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)g_2(x).$$

Dividing out an $(x - 1)$ and power of x gives the representation that we want with $j' = 15 - j$. Likewise we can get the first from the second. \square

The concept of good or bad is well defined and we have a parity type relationship.

Lemma 6. *An element ξ in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$, where $\gcd(N_{15}(\xi), 15) = 1$, cannot be both good and bad, and 1 is bad. If ξ_1, ξ_2 are both good or both bad, then $\xi_1\xi_2$ is bad, otherwise $\xi_1\xi_2$ is good. The conjugates of ξ are either all good or all bad.*

Proof. We rule out $F(x)$ being both good and bad; that is,

$$u_1((x^5 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x) + g_4(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x))$$

equalling

$$u_2 \left(\Phi_5(x) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x) + g_5(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x) \right).$$

Taking a basis $(x - 1), (x + 1), (x^3 + 1)$ for the units, moving any negative powers to the other side, we obtain equality at the 15th roots of unity and hence a polynomial identity:

$$\begin{aligned} \pm x^k(x - 1)^{r_1}(x + 1)^{s_1}(1 + x^3)^{t_1} \left((x^5 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x) \right) = \\ (x - 1)^{r_2}(x + 1)^{s_2}(1 + x^3)^{t_2} \left(\Phi_5(x) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x) \right) + g(x)\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x) + h(x)\Phi_{15}(x). \end{aligned}$$

Observing that $\Phi_{15}(\omega_3) = -5\omega_3, \Phi_{15}(\omega_5) = 3(\omega_5^3 + 1)$, taking N_3 and N_5 gives

$$3^{r_1+1}4^{t_1} \equiv 3^{r_2}4^{t_2} \pmod{5}, \quad 5^{r_1} \equiv 5^{r_2} \pmod{3},$$

but the first requires r_1, r_2 to have opposite parity and the second the same parity. Since $(x^5 - 1) - (x^3 - 1)$ is a unit we see that 1 (or any unit) must be bad.

Observe that the product of a bad and a good case gives a good case and the product of two good or two bad cases a bad case; essentially this is the parity of the power of $(x - 1)$ on the $\Phi_3(x)$ and $\Phi_5(x)$ terms, but to be explicit the product leads to

$$u \left((x^5 - 1)(x - 1)\Phi_5(x) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x)\Phi_3(x)B_1(x)B_2(x) \right) \pmod{\Phi_3(x)\Phi_5(x)}.$$

If one is bad, say $B_1(x) = (x - 1)$, then we can write $\Phi_5(x) = \Phi_3(x) + x^3(x + 1)$ and factor out the $x^3(x + 1)(x - 1)$ to get $u((x^5 - 1) \mp x^j \Phi_3(x)B_2(x))$ and we get good or bad as the other is good or bad. In the case both are good $B_1(x) = B_2(x) = 1$ we write $\Phi_5(x) = -x^5 + (1 + x^3)\Phi_3(x)$ and $\Phi_3(x) = (x - 1)^2 + 3x$ and factoring out $-x^5(x - 1)$ produces a bad case.

Notice also if $F(x)$ gives a good or bad case, then so do all its conjugates $F(x^k)$, $\gcd(k, 15) = 1$. To see this observe that $(x^{5k} - 1) = (x^5 - 1)t(x)$ where

$$t(x) = (1 + x^5 + \dots + x^{5(k-1)}) \equiv 1 \text{ or } -x^{10} \pmod{\Phi_3(x)} \text{ as } k \equiv 1 \text{ or } 2 \pmod{3}.$$

When $\Phi_3(x)B(x) = (x^3 - 1)$ we use $(x^{3k} - 1) = (x^3 - 1)t_2(x)$ where $t_2(x) = 1 + x^3 + \dots + x^{3(k-1)} \pmod{\Phi_5(x)}$ takes the form $1, 1 + x^3, 1 + x^3 + x^6 = -x^2(1 + x^2), -x^{12}$ as $k \equiv 1, 2, 3$ or $4 \pmod{5}$, which can all be removed to return to a bad case. In the good case we multiply by the unit $(x^k - 1)$ where $1 + x + \dots + x^{k-1} \equiv 1$ or $-x^2 \pmod{\Phi_3(x)}$ enabling $(x - 1)$ to be factored out to return to a good form. \square

Recalling that $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$ has uniqueness of factorization we can see that we can divide the primes in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$, not dividing 15, into those with good or bad representations and a product of these will be good if and only if it contains an odd number of good primes (unchanged by which conjugate is used). In particular for an integer

k which is a 15-norm, $k = N_{15}(\xi)$, $\gcd(k, 15) = 1$, it makes sense to say that k is 15-norm good or bad as ξ is good or bad. In particular a k will be 15-norm good if and only if its factorization in \mathbb{Z} contains an odd number of 15-norm good prime powers $p^r = N_{15}(\mathcal{P})$, where \mathcal{P} is a good prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$.

Finally we can obtain the multiples of any integer which is 15-norm good.

Lemma 7. *We can obtain 3^2k and 5^2k as a 15×15 circulant determinant for any k , $\gcd(k, 15) = 1$, which is 15-norm good.*

Proof. If k is 15-norm good, then $k = N_{15}(F)$ for an F of the form

$$F(x) = (x^5 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_3(x) + (x - 1) \Phi_3(x) \Phi_5(x) g_1(x)$$

and $M_{15}(F) = \pm 3^2k$ with $N_1(F) = \pm 3$, $N_3(F) = 3$ and $N_5(F) = 1$.

Likewise we get $\pm 5^2k$ from $F(x) = (x^3 - 1) \pm x^j \Phi_5(x) + (x - 1) \Phi_3(x) \Phi_5(x) g_2(x)$. □

5. Proof of Theorem 3

In this section we prove the following theorem.

Theorem 4. *If F is in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ and $M_{15}(F) = 3^2m$ or 5^2m with $\gcd(15, m) = 1$, then either $N_{15}(F)$ is 15-norm good, or $p \mid N_3(F)$ for some prime $p \equiv 7$ or $13 \pmod{15}$, or $p \mid N_5(F)$ for some prime $p \equiv 11 \pmod{15}$.*

From Lemma 7 we know that we can achieve $k3^2$ and $k5^2$ when k is 15-norm good and in the next section we show that we can achieve 3^2p and 5^2p whenever $p \equiv 7, 11$ or $13 \pmod{15}$. We can achieve any multiple m of these with $\gcd(m, 15) = 1$. So these are exactly the 15×15 determinant values.

To complete the proof of Theorem 3 we observe that a 15-norm good k must contain at least one 15-norm good prime power $p^r = N_{15}(\mathcal{P})$ where \mathcal{P} is a good prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$. We characterize these p^r in Section 7.

Proof. Suppose $F \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ has $M_{15}(F) = 3^2k$ or 5^2k , $\gcd(k, 15) = 1$. Since $N_3(F) \equiv F(1)^2 \pmod{3}$, $N_{15}(F) \equiv N_5(F)^2 \pmod{3}$, $N_5(F) \equiv F(1)^4 \pmod{5}$, $N_{15}(F) \equiv N_3(F)^4 \pmod{5}$, and since 3 and 5 remain irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_5]$ and $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_3]$ respectively we cannot have $3 \parallel N_5(F)$ or $5 \parallel N_3(F)$, we must have $\gcd(15, N_{15}(F)) = 1$ and $3 \nmid N_5(F)$, $5 \nmid N_3(F)$ and in the first case $3 \parallel F(1)$, $N_3(F) = 3m_1$, $N_5(F) = m_2$, $\gcd(m_1m_2, 15) = 1$ and in the second $5 \parallel F(1)$, $N_3(F) = m_1$, $N_5(F) = 5m_2$, $\gcd(m_1m_2, 15) = 1$.

Suppose that we have a Type 2 decomposition, that is, Equation (7) with $B(x)$ from List (9). Observe that all the $B(x)$ of Type 2 have $N_5(B(x)) = 5$ or 11 . Since

$\Phi_{15}(\omega_5) = 3(1 + \omega_5^3)$, $\Phi_{15}(\omega_3) = -5\omega_3$ we obtain

$$N_5(F) \equiv 5^i \cdot 2 \equiv (-1)^{i+1} \pmod{3}, \quad N_3(F) \equiv 3^{i+1} \pmod{5}.$$

Suppose that i is even, then in the first case $m_2 \equiv -1 \pmod{3}$ so the factorization of m_2 must contain an odd power of a prime $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. Since the power is odd the prime must split completely in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_5]$ so must be $1 \pmod{5}$. That is, $N_5(F)$ must contain a prime $p \equiv 11 \pmod{15}$. In the second case we get $m_1 \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$. Hence m_1 must contain an odd power of a prime $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ and since it is an odd power in $N_3(F)$ must be $1 \pmod{3}$. That is, $p \equiv 7$ or $13 \pmod{15}$.

If i is odd, then in the first case $m_1 \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ and in the second $m_2 \equiv -1 \pmod{3}$ with the same conclusions.

If we have a Type 1 decomposition, then, as in the proof of Lemma 5, $N_{15}(F)$ is 15-norm good. \square

6. Obtaining 3^2p and 5^2p for $p \equiv 7, 11$ or $13 \pmod{15}$.

To show that we obtain 3^2p and 5^2p for all the $p \equiv 7$ or $13 \pmod{15}$ we begin by showing that these primes must be 3-norms of a particular form.

Lemma 8. *If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then*

$$p = N_3(a + bx + 5(Ax + B))$$

for some $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $(a, b) = (1, 0), (2, 0), (3, 1), (4, 3)$ as $p \equiv 1, 4, 7, 13 \pmod{15}$.

If $p \equiv 7$ or $13 \pmod{15}$, then

$$p = N_3(a + bx + 5(x - 1)(Cx + D))$$

for some $C, D \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $(a, b) = (2, 3)$ or $(3, -1)$ as $p \equiv 7$ or $13 \pmod{15}$.

Proof of Lemma 8. Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, we know that p splits in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_3]$ and

$$p = N_3(\alpha + \beta x) = \alpha^2 + \beta^2 - \alpha\beta,$$

for some integers α, β , and we can write $\alpha + \beta x = a + bx + 5(Ax + B)$ with $a, b \in \{0, \pm 1, \pm 2\}$, not both zero since $5^2 \nmid p$. Observe that the norm remains unchanged if we switch the positions of α and β or multiply by -1 ; that is, we can replace (a, b) by (b, a) or $(-a, -b)$ on replacing $Ax + B$ by $Bx + A$ or $-Ax - B$. Hence we can assume that $a = 1$ or 2 and $|b| \leq a$.

If $b = 0$ that gives us $(2, 0)$ or $(1, 0)$. We can also replace $\alpha + \beta\omega_3$ by its conjugate $\alpha + \beta\omega_3^2$, and hence (a, b) by $(a - b, -b)$, on replacing $Ax + B$ by $-Ax + (B - A)$. Hence (a, a) reduces to $(0, -a)$ and thence to $(1, 0)$ or $(2, 0)$. Similarly, $(1, -1)$

reduces to $(2, 1)$ and $(2, -2) \mapsto (4, 2) \mapsto (-1, 2) \mapsto (2, -1)$. This just leaves $(2, 1) \mapsto (-3, -4) \mapsto (4, 3)$ or $(2, -1) \mapsto (-3, -1) \mapsto (3, 1)$. Since $p \equiv a^2 - ab + b^2 \pmod{5}$ these four types $(a, b) = (1, 0), (2, 0), (3, 1), (4, 3)$ correspond to the four possibilities mod 15.

Notice that for $p = 7$ or $13 \pmod{15}$ we could alternatively take $(2, -1) \mapsto (2, -2) \mapsto (2, 3)$ or $(2, 1) \mapsto (-3, 1) \mapsto (3, -1)$ and write $p = N_3(c + dx + 5(Ax + B))$ with $(c, d) = (2, 3)$ or $(3, -1)$ respectively.

Now if $A + B = 3m + r, r = 0, \pm 1$ we have

$$Ax + B = A(x - 1) - m(x - 1)(x + 2) + r \pmod{\Phi_3(x)},$$

and we can write $p = N_3(c + dx + 5r + 5(x - 1)(Cx + D))$. If $r = 0$ we are done. We can also rule out $r = -1$ as $3 \mid N_3(-3 + 3x), N_3(-2 - x)$. If $p = 7 \pmod{15}$ and $r = 1$ we write

$$\begin{aligned} p &= N_3(2 + 3x + 5x^2 + 5(x - 1)(Cx + D) - 5(x^2 - 1)) \\ &= N_3(-3 - 2x + 5(x - 1)(C_1x + D_1)) \\ &= N_3(-x(-3 - 2x^2 + 5(x^2 - 1)(C_1x^2 + D_1))) \\ &= N_3(2 + 3x + 5(x - 1)(C_2x + D_2)). \end{aligned}$$

If $p = 13 \pmod{15}$ and $r = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} p &= N_3(3 + 4x + 5(x - 1)(Cx + D - 1)) \\ &= N_3(-x^2(3 + 4x^2 + 5(x^2 - 1)(Cx^2 + D - 1))) \\ &= N_3(3 - x + 5(x - 1)(C_1x + D_1)). \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

We can use the A, B and C, D from Lemma 8 to obtain 3^2p and 5^2p .

Theorem 5. *If $p \equiv 7 \pmod{15}$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} M_{15}(1 - x + x^3\Phi_3(x^3) + (1 - x)\Phi_5(x)\Phi_{15}(x)(Ax + B)) &= 3^2p, \\ M_{15}(1 - x^2 + x^4 + x^9 + x^{10} + x^{13} + x^{14} + (x - 1)\Phi_5(x)\Phi_{15}(x)(Cx + D)) &= 5^2p. \end{aligned}$$

If $p \equiv 13 \pmod{15}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} M_{15}(1 - x^5 - x^{11} + x^{12} + x^3\Phi_3(x^3) + (1 - x)\Phi_5(x)\Phi_{15}(x)(Ax + B)) &= 3^2p, \\ M_{15}(1 + x^3 + x^6 + x^9 + x^{14} + (x - 1)\Phi_5(x)\Phi_{15}(x)(Cx + D)) &= 5^2p. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Denote the first and second polynomials by F and G . Observing that

$$N_1N_5N_{15}(1 - x + x^3\Phi_3(x^3)) = N_1N_5N_{15}(1 - x^5 - x^{11} + x^{12} + x^3\Phi_3(x^3)) = 3,$$

plainly $N_1N_5N_{15}(F) = 3$. We have $\Phi_5(\omega_3)\Phi_{15}(\omega_3) = 5$,

$$1 - \omega_3 + 3 = (1 - \omega_3)(3 + \omega_3), \quad 1 - \omega_3^5 - \omega_3^{11} + \omega_3^{12} + 3 = (1 - \omega_3)(4 + 3\omega_3)$$

and hence $N_3(F) = N_3(1 - x)N_3(a + bx + 5(Ax + B)) = 3p$.

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} N_1N_5N_{15}(1 - x^2 + x^4 + x^9 + x^{10} + x^{13} + x^{14}) &= 5^2, \\ N_1N_5N_{15}(1 + x^3 + x^6 + x^9 + x^{14}) &= 5^2, \end{aligned}$$

and $N_1N_5N_{15}(G) = 5^2$. Since

$$1 - \omega_3^2 + \omega_3^4 + \omega_3^9 + \omega_3^{10} + \omega_3^{13} + \omega_3^{14} = 2 + 3\omega_3, 1 + \omega_3^3 + \omega_3^6 + \omega_3^9 + \omega_3^{14} = 3 - \omega_3,$$

we get $N_3(G) = N_3(c + dx + 5(x - 1)(Cx + D)) = p$. □

To show that we can obtain all the 3^2p and 5^2p with $p \equiv 11 \pmod{15}$ we need a similar 5-norm representation lemma.

Lemma 9. *If $p \equiv 11 \pmod{15}$, then*

$$p = N_5(3 \pm (x - 1) + 3(x - 1)g(x))$$

for some $g(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, and $M_{15}(F) = 3^2p$ for

$$F(x) = 1 + x^5 + x^{10} \pm (x - 1) + (1 + x^5 + x^{10})(x - 1)g(x). \tag{10}$$

We can also write

$$5p = N_5((1 - x)(1 + 2x) + 3(1 - x)g_2(x))$$

for some $g_2(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, and $M_{15}(G) = 5^2p$ for

$$G(x) = x^{13}(1 + x + x^2 + x^3) - x^7 + x^{10} + x^{11} + (1 + x^5 + x^{10})(1 - x)g_2(x). \tag{11}$$

Proof. Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$ we know that p splits completely in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_5]$ and $p = N_5(F(x))$ for some $F \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Replacing $F(x)$ by $\pm F(x), \pm(x + 1)F(x)$ we can assume that $F(1) \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$. Hence we can write

$$\begin{aligned} F(x) &= 3 + 5m + (x - 1)g_1(x) \\ &= 3 + (x - 1)g_2(x), \quad g_2(x) = g_1(x) + m(x^2 - 1)(x^3 - 1)(x^4 - 1) \\ &= 3 + (x - 1)h(x) + 3(x - 1)g_3(x), \quad h(x) = \sum_{j=0}^3 a_j x^j, \quad a_j \in \{0, \pm 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proceeding as in the proof of Lemma 5 we can reduce to $h(x) = \pm x^j B(x)$ with $B(x)$ of Type 1, List (8), or Type 2, List (9). But the Type 2 have $N_5(B(x)) = 5$ or 11, resulting in $N_5(F) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. So we can assume that

$$p = N_5(3 \pm x^j(x - 1)B(x) + 3(x - 1)g(x)), \quad B(x) = 1, x + 1, x^2 + 1 \text{ or } x^2 - x + 1.$$

If $B(x) = x + 1$ we can make the substitution $x \mapsto x^3$ to make the $(x - 1)B(x) = (x^2 - 1) \mapsto (x - 1)$. Writing $(x^2 - x + 1)^{-1} = \prod_{j=2}^4 (x^{2j} - x^j + 1) = 1 + (x - 1)g_3(x)$ we can divide out $B(x) = (x^2 - x + 1)$. If $B(x) = x^2 + 1$, then $x \mapsto x^3$ makes $(x - 1)B(x) \mapsto (x^3 - 1)(x + 1) = (x - 1)B(x)$, with

$$B(x) = (x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1) = 6 + (x - 1)g_3(x) = 1 + (x - 1)g_4(x),$$

but in this case $B(x)^{-1} = \prod_{j=2}^4 B(x^j) = 1 + (x - 1)g_5(x)$ and we can again divide by $B(x)$. This leaves $B(x) = 1$ and we can divide out any x^j by multiplying through by $x^{4j} = 1 + (x - 1)g_4(x)$.

For the $F(x)$ given in Equation (10) we have $N_1(F) = 3$, $N_3N_{15}(F) = N_3N_{15}(\pm(x - 1)) = 3$ while $N_5(F) = N_5(3 \pm (x - 1) + 3(x - 1)g(x)) = p$.

We can write

$$\begin{aligned} 5p &= N_5(\pm(x - 1)(3 \pm (x - 1) + 3(x - 1)g(x))) \\ &= N_5((1 - x)(1 + 2x) + 3(1 - x)g_2(x)), \quad g_2(x) = -x \mp 1 \pm (1 - x)g(x). \end{aligned}$$

For the $G(x)$ given in Equation (11) we have

$$N_1N_3N_{15}(G) = N_1N_3N_{15}(x^{13}(1 + x + x^2 + x^3) - x^7 + x^{10} + x^{11}) = 5$$

while

$$\omega_5^{13}(1 + \omega_5 + \omega_5^2 + \omega_5^3) - \omega_5^7 + \omega_5^{10} + \omega_5^{11} = (1 - \omega_5)(1 + 2\omega_5)$$

and $N_5(G) = N_5((1 - x)(1 + 2x) + 3(1 - x)g_2(x)) = 5p$. □

7. Primes in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$

Finally, to simplify the statement of Theorem 3, we need a lemma to say how the primes split in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$.

Lemma 10. *The primes $p \neq 3, 5$ factor in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_{15}]$ as*

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{15} \Rightarrow p = \mathcal{P}_1 \cdots \mathcal{P}_8, \quad N_{15}(\mathcal{P}_i) = p, \quad (12)$$

$$p \equiv 4, 11 \text{ or } 14 \pmod{15} \Rightarrow p = \mathcal{P}_1 \cdots \mathcal{P}_4, \quad N_{15}(\mathcal{P}_i) = p^2, \quad (13)$$

$$p \equiv 2, 7, 8 \text{ or } 13 \pmod{15} \Rightarrow p = \mathcal{P}_1\mathcal{P}_2, \quad N_{15}(\mathcal{P}_i) = p^4. \quad (14)$$

For the remaining primes $5 = u_1(1 - \omega_5)^4$, $3 = u_2(1 - \omega_3)^2$ for some units u_1, u_2 .

Proof. Recall (eg Washington [24, Theorem 2.13]) that $p \nmid n$ splits into $\phi(n)/f$ distinct primes in $\mathbb{Q}(\omega_n)$ each of which have residue class degree f , where f is the smallest positive integer with $p^f \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. When $n = 15$ plainly $f = 1$ if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$, $f = 2$ if $p \equiv 4, 11 \text{ or } 14 \pmod{15}$ and $f = 4$ if $p \equiv 2, 7, 8 \text{ or } 13 \pmod{15}$.

Similarly, 3 and 5 stay prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_5]$ and $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_3]$ but ramify completely on adding ω_3 or ω_5 . Since $\mathbb{Q}(\omega_{15})$ has class number one we can replace prime ideals with prime elements. \square

Hence if k , $\gcd(k, 15) = 1$, is a 15-norm, then it consists of products of p with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$, p^2 with $p \equiv 4, 11$ or $14 \pmod{15}$, and p^4 with $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$. A 15-norm good k must be divisible by at least one of these p or p^2 or p^4 which is 15-norm good. For the $p \equiv 1 \pmod{15}$ it is hard to predict which p are good or bad, and for $p \equiv 7, 11$ or 13 we can otherwise achieve all multiples p . For the remaining p^2 , $p \equiv 4$ or $14 \pmod{15}$ and p^4 with $p \equiv 2$ or $8 \pmod{15}$ we can determine this.

Lemma 11. *If $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$, then p^4 is 15-norm good.*

Of course if $p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$, then p^2 is a 15-norm and its square is 15-norm bad.

Proof. Since $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ we know that p remains irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_5]$.

Suppose that $p^4 = N_{15}(F(x))$ has a bad representation

$$F(x) = (x^5 - 1) \pm x^j(x^3 - 1) + (x^3 - 1)(x^5 - 1)g(x).$$

Writing $G(x) = F(x\omega_3)F(x\omega_3^2)$ we have $G(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ with $p^4 = N_5(G(x))$. Hence for x a primitive 5th root of unity we have $H(x) = G(x)G(x^{-1}) = |F(x)|^2$ in $\mathbb{Z}[\frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5})]$, the integers in the real subfield of the 5th roots of unity, and

$$H(x) = u_1 p^2, \quad H(x^2) = u_2 p^2, \quad u_1 = \left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5})\right)^{2k}, \quad u_2 = \left(\frac{1}{2}(1 - \sqrt{5})\right)^{2k},$$

for some k in \mathbb{Z} (notice that u_1 and its conjugate u_2 under $x \rightarrow x^2$, $\sqrt{5} \rightarrow -\sqrt{5}$, must both be positive and so must be an even power $2k$ of the fundamental unit). Expanding

$$\begin{aligned} G(x) &= ((\omega_3^2 - 1) \pm (x\omega_3)^j(x^3 - 1) + (x^3 - 1)(\omega_3^2 - 1)g(x\omega_3)) \\ &\quad ((\omega_3 - 1) \pm (x\omega_3^2)^j(x^3 - 1) + (x^3 - 1)(\omega_3 - 1)g(x\omega_3^2)) \\ &= 3 + x^{2j}(x^3 - 1)^2 + 3(x^3 - 1)t_1(x), \end{aligned}$$

and for $x = \omega_5$

$$H(x) = G(x)G(x^{-1}) = 9 + \frac{5}{2}(3 + \sqrt{5}) + 3\sqrt{5} t_2 \left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5})\right).$$

Writing $\left(\frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)^k = \frac{1}{2}(a_k + b_k \sqrt{5})$ we have $a_k p^2 = H(x) + H(x^2) = 33 + 15m$ and, since $p^2 \equiv -1 \pmod{5}$, we must have $a_k \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $a_k \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$. But it is readily checked that the $(a_k \pmod{3}, a_k \pmod{5})$ cycle through the values $(0, -2), (1, 2), (0, -2), (2, 2)$ never $(0, 2)$. Hence p^4 must have a good representation. \square

Lemma 12. *If $p \equiv 4 \pmod{15}$, then p^2 is 15-norm good. If $p \equiv 14 \pmod{15}$, then p^2 is 15-norm bad.*

Proof. We proceed as in the proof Lemma 11, except that when $p \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$ we know that p factors in the real subfield of the 5th roots of unity $p = \alpha^2 - 5\beta^2 = (\alpha + \beta\sqrt{5})(\alpha - \beta\sqrt{5})$ (plainly $x^2 + x - 1$ factors mod p since $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{p}{5}\right) = 1$), with $\alpha \pm \beta\sqrt{5}$ remaining prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega_5]$ (fixed by $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ and interchanged by $x \mapsto x^2$). Hence this time

$$H(x) = \frac{1}{2}(a_k + b_k\sqrt{5}) \left(\alpha + \beta\sqrt{5}\right)^2, \quad H(x^2) = \frac{1}{2}(a_k - b_k\sqrt{5}) \left(\alpha - \beta\sqrt{5}\right)^2,$$

giving

$$H(x) + H(x^2) = (\alpha^2 + 5\beta^2)a_k + 10\alpha\beta b_k.$$

Suppose that $p \equiv 4 \pmod{15}$ and that we have a bad representation, then as before

$$H(x) + H(x^2) = 33 + 15m.$$

Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ we know that $3 \mid \alpha\beta$ and $\alpha^2 \equiv p \equiv -1 \pmod{5}$. Hence $-a_k \equiv -2 \pmod{5}$ and $0 \equiv \pm a_k \pmod{3}$, but as before $(a_k \pmod{3}, a_k \pmod{5})$ is not $(0, 2)$. So the representation for p^2 must be good.

Suppose that $p \equiv 14 \pmod{15}$ and that p^2 has a good representation:

$$F(x) = (x^5 - 1)(x - 1) \pm x^j(x^3 - 1) + (x^3 - 1)(x^5 - 1)g(x).$$

Then, for x a primitive 5th root of unity,

$$G(x) = 3(1 + x + x^2) + x^{2j}(x^3 - 1)^2 + 3(x^3 - 1)t(x)$$

and for $x = \omega_5$

$$H(x) = \frac{9}{2}(3 + \sqrt{5}) + \frac{5}{2}(3 + \sqrt{5}) + 3\sqrt{5}t_2 \left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5})\right),$$

and

$$H(x) + H(x^2) = 42 + 15m.$$

Hence $-a_k \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$. Since $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ we have $3 \nmid \alpha\beta$ and $\alpha^2 + 5\beta^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $\pm b_k \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. But $(a_k \pmod{5}, b_k \pmod{3})$ cycles through $(-2, 1), (2, 0), (-2, -1), (2, 0)$ never $(-2, 0)$. So p^2 must have a bad representation. \square

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